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FutureTDM

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REDUCING BARRIERS AND INCREASING UPTAKE OF TEXT AND DATA MINING FOR RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS USING A COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE AND OPEN INFORMATION APPROACH

Deliverable D7.2

FutureTDM Communication and Exploitation Plan

Project

Acronym: **FutureTDM**

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is designed to meet the overall objective of FutureTDM – to identify and remove TDM uptake barriers in the EU through an effective and sustainable communications strategy. It sets out a strategy to engage, to inform (showing our expertise), to be accessible and to be relevant now and post project end date.

The plan explains how we are going to communicate the project, offering options both on-line and in person, with user friendly language and a recognisable slogan. Much of the communications strategy draws from other work packages and in particular work package 2, with a strong emphasis on engaging with the stakeholders identified in D2.2. With inclusion at its core, the communications plan aims to attract an invested TDM community, to inform them about TDM best practice and latest developments. Because the project has to appeal to a wide variety of stakeholders, the language and tone of the communication methods are important. Underlying all our activities is the proactive message: Help us to help you, join the FutureTDM community to improve TDM uptake in the EU. The plan runs in two phases with the first 10 months focussed on encouraging stakeholder feedback. Thereafter, communicating the Open Information Hub will become the priority. The Exploitation section of the plan lays out how the project sustainability will be addressed after September 2017. A table overview of project communications methods, responsibility and targets can be found in Annex 1.

2 PROJECT SUMMARY AS A BACKGROUND TO THE COMMUNICATIONS PLAN

Text and data mining (TDM) enables researchers from different disciplines to analyse, extract insights and knowledge, and exploit large diverse and complex datasets from various digital media. This information is growing at an incredible rate to the point where it is often described as big data. Harnessing it effectively via TDM offers an opportunity to address some of society's grand challenges including disease control and climate change mitigation. At present, use of TDM in Europe is significantly lower than in parts of the Americas and Asia, possibly due to limitations imposed by the European legal framework. Through its activities and outputs, FutureTDM aims to improve uptake of text and data mining in the EU.

In communicating the project it is worth remembering these project activities. FutureTDM identifies and reduces the barriers that inhibit the uptake of TDM for researchers, and other stakeholders. FutureTDM provides critical up-to-date assessments of legal regulations and policies impacting TDM in the EU, and places them in the international research and innovation context. It adopts a bottom-up approach by initiating dialogue between all relevant stakeholders, engaging them via knowledge cafés, workshops and with expert representation on the FutureTDM advisory board to help identify barriers, common solutions and increase awareness of TDM practices and their potential. This combined approach will lead to developing novel policy frameworks and interdisciplinary case-driven practitioner guidelines facilitating the spread of TDM activities.

Key to success will be the engagement of actors in the broader community (library, SME, publishing, funding, policy etc.), who will be mobilised through workshops and will be provided with recommendations in the Roadmap for TDM uptake. The knowledge distilled from quantitative and qualitative research will be integrated into a Collaborative Knowledge Base and Open Information Hub using insightful visualisations. This dynamic platform will showcase excellence in TDM research and data-driven innovation and serve as reference for current and future TDM practitioners ensuring broader TDM uptake to boost Europe's research and innovation capacities.

A strong element of the FutureTDM Project is therefore in its engagement with stakeholders both in identifying barriers and solutions to TDM uptake and providing a platform for their engagement. Communicating with TDM stakeholders in an effective way throughout all stages of the project will be crucial.

3 COMMUNICATIONS AND EXPLOITATION PLAN: INTRODUCTION

The Communications and Exploitation Plan sets out how the project will raise awareness about FutureTDM and communicate its findings to targeted stakeholder groups and end-users. It is part of Work Package 7 (WP7) Disseminate, which covers project communication, publications, mobilisation and networking and it is summarized in Figure 1.

WP7 Objectives (in order of production)

- To develop a creative project website to relay timely information about project activities and accomplishments to the public. In addition, social media channels will be exploited to increase project awareness and stimulate stakeholder participation.
- To produce the communication and exploitation plan in the early stages of the project to build sound approaches for networking and outreach.
- To create stimulating dissemination materials (leaflets, newsletters, etc.) to distribute over multiple channels using on-line and print media to promote the FutureTDM project.
- To organise a Symposium, a culmination of the project's events, to connect key actors and interest groups to promote open dialogue via discussion panels and informal workshops.

This plan sets out step-by-step how the communication objectives will be achieved, making the best use of our strengths, achievements and influential network of enthusiastic partners.

The tasks of this Work Package are oriented to achieve project Objective #6: INCREASE awareness of TDM to especially attract new target groups and science domains by creating a roadmap, run mobilisation and engagement activities and provide information material and modern TDM visualisations and info-graphics.

Figure 1: Communication and exploitation plan

4 FUTURETDM COMMUNICATIONS AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

– SETTING THE SCENE

In executing this Communication and Exploitation Plan, the project aims to ensure a broad reach of FutureTDM and to promote its activities and findings among target groups identified in WP2 and WP3. The Exploitation section of the plan will specifically deal with the long-term sustainability and usability of the platform, policy framework, and practitioner guidelines beyond the end of the project lifespan. Communication, dissemination and awareness raising activities will be evaluated in a Summary Report at the end of the project. The FutureTDM Communication Plan is the result of consultation with all partners but in particular work packages 2 and 7, the stakeholder engagement and disseminations groups of the project.

4.1 A Two Phase Project

The FutureTDM project runs over two years with the first year broadly committed to gathering information and mapping the TDM landscape and the second year focussing more on developing solutions, best practices and the establishment of the online platform known as the Open Information Hub. The communication strategy will therefore need to be flexible. In the first instance the emphasis will be put into the communication of project goals to the stakeholder community and inviting feedback and event attendance. In the second year attention shifts to highlighting the opportunities associated with TDM, and fostering collaboration and uptake. Stakeholders will be directed to the Open Information Hub and any other documentation produced by the project.

4.2 All About Engagement

FutureTDM is all about engagement. The dissemination activities in WP7 are closely linked to the objectives of WP2, stakeholder engagement. In WP2 it was established that by stakeholder engagement we mean a process that involves people or organisations affected by the project, or who can influence the implementation of its decisions. It was also emphasised that stakeholder engagement is a two-way process. This is in contrast to dissemination, which is mainly one-way and simply sends out messages about decisions already taken to inform or influence the audience. Because of this, the goals of deliverable 7.2 are designed to ensure that they encourage project awareness, inclusion and collaboration.

Although LIBER are responsible for drafting this communication and exploitation plan, OK/CM are responsible for the overall dissemination Work Package 7. All nine partners will have a role in ensuring the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination aspects of the project. Their individual responsibilities will be explained further in this plan.

5 KEY OBJECTIVES

The Communication Plan will pave the way for the broadest possible awareness of the project through clear and informative communications.

The project will enable partners and stakeholders to exploit the “multiplier effect”, sharing news and project developments with their own community of professionals, decision makers and end users. To do this, the Communications Plan will provide the necessary tools for partners and stakeholders to undertake this dissemination work, both through physical and virtual materials.

FutureTDM will involve stakeholders in the communications process by offering multiple opportunities to participate in the project’s work at EU events, FutureTDM workshops, knowledge cafés and the Symposium. The project will also give stakeholders the opportunity to share written feedback and expertise with the project via social media, blogs and surveys.

The aim of the communications plan is to build an invested and growing TDM community that can serve as an ever-larger soundboard for the project. Communications activities will inform stakeholders of the TDM landscape and latest developments as well as the benefits of becoming involved in the project and collaborating with others.

It is also hoped that the project can enable stakeholders to improve on their own work processes by sharing the project’s best practice achievements, recommendations and outcomes.

The Communications Plan objectives are linked to the two phases of the project. In the first instance, the aim is to generate a “buzz” around the project and encourage participation in the engagement activities, to build a sense of belonging and to get feedback from the TDM stakeholder community. This in turn will boost the communications aim of the second phase of FutureTDM, namely to ensure usage of the Open Information Hub and to ensure that the community provides content.

If these communications objectives are successful, then the project goal of identifying barriers and solutions to TDM uptake can be met.

6 TARGET AUDIENCE

The target audience of the project, as identified in D2.2, are the following:

- **Research community**
Supply content providers with text and data, further knowledge discovery with mined data
- **TDM Content Providers**
Holders of content that can be mined. May also offer a service
- **Consumers of TDM**
Sectors that look to benefit from knowledge discovery, may form public private partnerships
- **Funders**
Economic drivers for TDM development
- **Policy Shapers**
Involved in the development of TDM legislation and influencing TDM policy
- **Service Providers**
Working with computer software. Improving the service interoperability, using TDM, enhancing TDM usability.
- **Information aggregators and analysts**
Identifying trends and patterns arising from TDM as their main function
- **Citizens**
Individuals with an interest in TDM, both users and providers of content

6.1 Stakeholder Identification

Stakeholders are identified through partner networks, attendance at TDM related events, requests to be added to the FutureTDM mailing list and where they are known actors in the TDM environment. Partner and project social media will be used to invite further stakeholder inclusion. A directory of stakeholders is available in the project shared drive for project partners to add to throughout the project. This will be used to communicate materials that arise from the project and to invite stakeholders to project events. It will be translated into an online stakeholder map, forming part of the Open Information Hub in year two of the project.

6.2 Maximising Existing Networks

There are nine project partners with well-developed networks. In addition to the project directory, partners will be using their own communications resources. In this way, the project is able to instantly reach hundreds of target stakeholders. For example, LIBER is a well-established library membership organisation that works with over 400 libraries in some 40 countries. In order to effectively communicate with its members, LIBER has already developed a number of communications channels. They include a website, multiple mailing lists, and accounts on the major social media networks.

Partners will be encouraged to share project news with their own colleagues and user communities. In addition, the partners have excellent ties with other key players in the international community, many of whom target the same stakeholders as the FutureTDM Project.

7 MESSAGING

A solid Communication Plan will ensure the wide dissemination of the project's objectives, results and achievements towards the identified stakeholder groups via a series of well-balanced messages in a recognisable format.

7.1 Messaging

Our key project communication messages are based on the project's slogan: '**Explore, analyse, improve**' and should run through our communications activity.

- **Explore:** FutureTDM will listen to stakeholders and map the current content mining landscape
- **Analyse:** FutureTDM will examine findings and with expert input, develop practical and policy solutions to increase TDM uptake in the EU
- **Improve:** FutureTDM's online Open Information Hub will publicise the latest TDM information, showcase best practice and facilitate stakeholder collaboration

Because of the technical nature of content mining and the variety of stakeholder backgrounds, from policy to developer, we should remember to make our communications user friendly. Where possible, the project goal should be visible; FutureTDM: Improving uptake of text and data mining in the EU.

In engaging with the TDM community, where relevant, the message should include a call to action; Help us to help you. Join the FutureTDM community to improve text and data mining uptake in the EU.

7.2 Brand

Figure 2: The FutureTDM logo

A consistent visual appearance of the project is a prerequisite for a successful media communication with stakeholders and end users. It guarantees a visual synergy with the FutureTDM brand and includes:

- A logo, with its own colour scheme, which can be incorporated into document templates
- The project slogan: Explore, Analyse, Improve. This will feature on the materials produced by the project as part of raising brand awareness

- Promotional materials designed to match the brand, with the logo prominently displayed (e.g. posters, flyer, leaflet, sticker etc.)

The brand will be kept visible via presentation of the project at relevant events, exhibitions, workshops and meetings, including distribution of the various promotional materials. This will be alongside a continuous media campaign (articles in journals, social media, videos, mailing lists, press releases, newsletters etc.).

SYNYO have developed the logo, slogan and visual style of the project, which will be incorporated into all promotional materials.

8 COMMUNICATION METHODS

As outlined in D2.2 the project communication methods are both virtual and physical and meet five engagement requirements:

ENGAGEMENT REQUIREMENT	Virtual tools	Physical tools
Stakeholders understand text and data mining	FutureTDM video Social media FutureTDM website/Open Information Hub Consortium websites	FutureTDM workshops Expert Advisory Board FutureTDM knowledge cafés Partners presenting at events Other project events Fact sheets Journal and conference publications
Stakeholders know about the goals and achievements of the FutureTDM project	FutureTDM Video Social media Power Point slides FutureTDM website/Open Information Hub Consortium websites FutureTDM newsletter Press releases Email lists Project reports	FutureTDM workshops/symposium FutureTDM knowledge cafés Presenting FutureTDM at events Surveys Fact sheets Posters/flyers Promo item – sticker
Stakeholders have the opportunity to feedback their experiences and feel comfortable doing so	Short videos Social media FutureTDM website/Open	FutureTDM workshops/symposium FutureTDM knowledge cafés

	<p>Information Hub</p> <p>Consortium websites</p> <p>Data Open Information Hub</p> <p>Blog space</p> <p>Online survey</p>	<p>Surveys</p> <p>Networking events</p> <p>Joint project events</p>
<p>Stakeholders have the opportunity to collaborate with each other</p>	<p>Open Information Hub</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>FutureTDM website/Open Information Hub</p> <p>Consortium websites</p> <p>Contacting consortium partners</p>	<p>FutureTDM workshops/symposium</p> <p>FutureTDM knowledge cafés</p> <p>Networking events</p> <p>Contacting consortium partners</p> <p>Joint project events</p>
<p>Synergies with other related projects, particularly OpenMinTed</p>	<p>Linked website with OpenMinTeD, re-tweets</p> <p>News/Blogs on project websites</p> <p>Newsletter mentions</p>	<p>Joint events</p> <p>Joint workshops</p> <p>Presentations at each-others events</p> <p>Joint materials i.e. posters</p>

Although this table outlines a number of communication tools, there are three main environments for communication that will now be looked at in more detail: internal project communications, stakeholder communication at events and engagement online.

9 INTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS

To ensure efficient project coordination, the FutureTDM consortium requires a user friendly internal communication structure.

SYNYO have set up an internal Google Drive where all documents relating to the project can be found. They include:

- The events directory and dissemination log – mapping opportunities and involvement
- The publications log – Partners planned publications and fact sheets and references
- The blog log – partners can add blogs here they would like to contribute
- Project deliverables
- Meeting agendas and minutes

The partners participate in google hang out calls every two weeks to provide updates on activities and discuss planning and progress. Further bilateral calls are arranged where necessary. SYNYO circulates minutes and agendas.

Partners share updates, reminders, web-links and documents by circulating their updates to the FutureTDM google groups email address.

Physical project meetings are scheduled to take place on a quarterly basis, the first (post Kick-Off) is taking place in Brussels on 26 February 2016.

Networking Co-ordination

In the shared google drive there is a project events directory where all partners can add the details of relevant upcoming events for the dissemination and networking of FutureTDM including dates, deadlines for submissions, location, event website and type of project presence (presentation, poster, paper, workshop attendance etc.).

Partners are encouraged to add to this, discuss events during the calls and attend. If they did attend they should note this in the shared document. In this way the document will become a sort of dissemination log. Upcoming events are also listed on the project website.

10 EVENTS

A strong aspect of the project is gaining feedback from stakeholders through a series of project events. The project will organise a programme of knowledge cafés, workshops and the FutureTDM Symposium. Along-side these events, dissemination of materials will take place at external conferences, workshops, meetings and at events hosted by other European Commission funded projects.

10.1 External Events

In collecting feedback and promoting general awareness of the project, external events directly support the expansion of our network to additional stakeholders. They give current partners the opportunity to identify new organisations that might join the network. At the same time, potential new stakeholders can experience first-hand the benefits of connecting with FutureTDM by listening to presentations about the project and learning about the results achieved. We will communicate the project at these events through project presentations and publicity materials. Where partners present on FutureTDM they should use the project power point template provided by SYNYO.

In this category of communication activities, the project has already held a joint workshop at the DISH2015 event in Rotterdam, presented at the ICT 2015 fair in Portugal and has secured a stall at the Stakeholder4EU digital forum in Brussels. With external events like these coming up all through the year we envisage a consistent FutureTDM presence, which will contribute to a high profile.

10.2 FutureTDM Events – Key Dates:

FutureTDM is organising a series of its own events (knowledge cafés, workshops and a symposium) aimed at stakeholder engagement. They are explained in D2.2. All workshops will cover technical, legal, economic and research infrastructure issues and where possible will be organised next to other relevant events. The intensity of dissemination activities on social media will be increased in the weeks leading up to the events, and will mainly focus on explaining the event, who is attending, why it is important and what will be discussed. After the event, a digest of the findings/event feedback will be disseminated as soon as possible:

- Externally via a write-up on the website blog
- Internally in more detail in an event evaluation form via the shared documents space

At present the knowledge cafés are scheduled as follows but it is expected that more events will be added as they arise and dates may change. This is to maximise stakeholder engagement and geographic diversity.

Knowledge cafés (core cafés in bold)	Date	Stakeholder community most closely linked to these locations
DISH 2015, Rotterdam, Netherlands	7 December 2015	Digital heritage sector
Leiden Centre for Data Science Leiden, Netherlands	29 February 2016	Researchers
British Library London, UK	7 March 2016	Research organisations and funders
Impact Hub Berlin, Germany	24 March 2016	SMEs/start-ups
London Book Fair (or nearby venue) London, UK	12 April 2016 - TBC	Publishers
LREC Conference Portorož, Slovenia	24 May 2016	Computer linguists
LIBER Conference Helsinki, Finland	29 June 2016	Research libraries
FutureTDM Workshop Brussels, Belgium	July 2016	Policy shapers

10.3 The Workshops

As outlined and described in D2.2, two project workshops will be arranged by LIBER in order to showcase the project findings. The first will focus on the TDM barriers identified in the information-gathering phase of the project. The second will highlight solutions to improve TDM uptake in the EU based on expert evaluation in the second phase of the project. Communication activities around the workshops will reflect these objectives and will be aimed at all stakeholder groups. Prior to the workshops, the project communication activities will focus on publicising the event to maximise participation. At the workshops themselves, project branding will be exploited and communications activities will centre on disseminating project resource materials and findings. These will also be made available on the website for stakeholders who could not attend. On the day of the workshops there will be a project press release and a media campaign as follow-up.

10.4 The Symposium

The Symposium represents the culmination of the project achievements. Communications activities will relay exactly what the project has produced over its two phases and how it will be of benefit to the TDM community. Accordingly, a major focus will be on projecting the Open Information Hub and importance of collaboration. Prior to the Symposium, the project communication activities will publicise the event to maximise participation. This will be a positive and dynamic event with a variety of communication methods in play on the day, including screening of project videos and interview clips, new materials resulting from the project findings and an eye catching infographic, as well as the more traditional dissemination materials - all prominently displaying the FutureTDM brand and platform website. On the day of the symposium there will be a project press release and a media campaign as follow-up.

11 A STRONG WEB PRESENCE

In the first year of the project, the website will be the main online communication space where stakeholders can find out more about FutureTDM activities. The project site is registered under two names: project.futuretdm.eu and also www.futuretdm.eu for ease of access for stakeholders.

Layout of the Project Website: Site – map

The structure of the FutureTDM website is extremely intuitive and it is illustrated in Figure 3. The homepage gives a first overview of the project and allows easily access to the other subsections. The most recent blog posts and tweets are visible on the home page (Figure2). Moreover, a short project video is also available, which presents the content and aims of FutureTDM.

Figure 3: Structure of FutureTDM Website

Relevant information about the project and the consortium can be found in the pages “Project Info” and “Consortium” respectively. The section “Events” contains the past and future venues where the project has been or will be presented. Similarly, the section “Resources” encompasses information about dissemination activities and printable materials such as factsheets, promotional materials, presentations and project logo. These items may be downloaded and shared. In this section of the website we also plan to highlight external resources in the public domain that are relevant to content mining such as explanation of the TDM process, useful links etc.

The most dynamic part of the website is the “Blog” section. Here TDM contributions from consortium partners and invited stakeholders are collected as well as topics related to the scope of the project in general. Any interested stakeholder can add a comment using his/her Facebook, Twitter, Google, or Disqus account. The comments are not immediately posted, but are moderated to guarantee a high quality content and to avoid spam. Finally, interested users can subscribe the newsletter and get in contact with the consortium using the official email address office@futuretdm.eu which can be found in the “Contact” section.

Figure 4: FutureTDM Website (Home)

Other communications tools will also be made available on the website, and visible from the home page. They include the survey and TDM video. Both are explained in more detail in the communications methods chapter. The survey will be launched at the same time as the face to face interviews (task 4.3). The website is not expected to remain static, the aim is to be user friendly and engaging so we anticipate that there will be changes to improve the website’s look (i.e. blank space will be filled) and functionality as the project progresses.

11.1 The Open Information Hub

In year two of the project, The Knowledge Hub and Collaborative website (The Open Information Hub) will take over from the project web page. A first version is expected in month 14. The Open Information Hub is summarised below and more information on this can be found in the deliverables relating to work package 6.

Aims of the Open Information Hub

- Become the go-to website about TDM
- Bring stakeholders together
- Provide TDM information and collaboration space to empower practitioners with the resources to promote the uptake of TDM in Europe

- Provide practical, legal and policy information on TDM
- Provide information on barriers and solutions to TDM
- Give those who are new to the topic a first introduction to the advantages of TDM
- Promote TDM through best practices
- Disseminate the FutureTDM and OpenMinTeD projects and any other projects related to TDM
- Encourage the online debate about TDM
- Build an interested, dedicated, contributing and returning TDM community

Content of the Open Information Hub Website

- Joint FutureTDM and OpenMinTeD blogs section which may be extended to other projects (month 14)
- Stakeholder and experts navigator and map (month 16)
- Best practices catalogue, based on interviews and research (month 20)
- Tool selector for inventory of tools, applications, platforms and vendors in the field of TDM
- Project and Initiatives database, coupled with the National Dashboards database (month 20)
- Legal guidance
- Practical guidance (application trends and practical guidelines) (month 23)
- Collaboration space – supports virtual dialogues between the project consortium and external experts / stakeholders
- Information: policy priorities, roadmaps, practitioner guidelines, visualisations, infographics, project accomplishment (month 23)

11.2 The Project Website After the Open Information Hub is Launched

The project website will remain but will only contain the project description, milestones achieved and information about the partners. The Home page will publicise and link to the Open Information Hub where all other information (twitter feed, events, resources and blog) will be moved.

11.3 Collaboration With OpenMinTeD

OpenMinTeD and FutureTDM run in parallel and are sister projects about text and data mining (TDM) in Europe. While OpenMinTeD has more of a technical focus, both projects want to increase awareness of text and data mining among stakeholders in Europe, showcase best practices and build a TDM community.

Both Description of Works of OpenMinTeD and FutureTDM highlight the necessary cooperation between the two projects. Through their (joint) workshops, knowledge cafés, online activities, presentations at events, dissemination activities, and project websites, OpenMinTeD and FutureTDM are both building a community involved in TDM.

The Open Information Hub and Collaborative Website, which will be built by FutureTDM's WP6, will be the place where we bring the FutureTDM and OpenMinTeD communities together. This will be done by making this website a place of TDM discussion, in the form of frequent blogs on TDM topics. All the blogs will be disseminated through the social media accounts of both OpenMinTeD and

FutureTDM. The first version of the Open Information Hub and Collaborative website should be finished by month 14. Later versions will be rolled out in the following months. Until month 14, both projects will blog on their own project websites until the Open Information Hub and Collaborative website is ready. Then the blogs will be transferred and both projects will publish all new blogs on this website.

The Open Information Hub collaboration between FutureTDM and OpenMinTeD is detailed further in the Exploitation Plan section of this deliverable.

12 COMMUNICATION METHODS EXPLAINED

This section of the Communications Plan looks in greater detail at the communication methods that the project will adopt, the responsibility for each method, the timing and targets. A table overview of all communications methods can be found in Annex 1

12.1 Ensuring Engagement - Videos, Blogs, Surveys and Social Media

As established in D2.2 one of the unique aspects of the FutureTDM project is the fact that it draws heavily from stakeholder involvement. Not everyone will be able to attend the FutureTDM events so the project must offer opportunity for stakeholders to provide feedback throughout the project and beyond. Accordingly four aspects of the communications strategy are designed for this purpose.

- A clear and accessible video that will explain the project and invite feedback. It will be shown on the website, the Open Information Hub, at events and promoted on twitter
- A blog section on the project website where stakeholders can either submit guest blogs or comment on blogs written by the project partners
- An online survey that is available on the project website/the Open Information Hub so that stakeholders have an opportunity to provide their opinion on the project
- A social media strategy that is engagement rather than dissemination focussed. Tweets may feature polls, ask for feedback tweets or promote the alternative engagement methods mentioned above

12.2 FutureTDM Videos

The project will produce at least two videos. One as a visualisation of the DoA which will be more relevant on a project management level, particularly for other projects to gain an insight into FutureTDM operations. Produced by SYNYO, it has already been publicised at events, and is on the project website.

A second video will be produced soon after the communications plan has been submitted. An accessible, clear short (approx 2 minutes) piece of media, aimed at all TDM interested stakeholders and understandable to every level of expertise, its message will be: Help us to help you, join the FutureTDM community to improve TDM uptake in the EU.

The video will be presented in a fun and engaging format, it will have the following elements:

- Setting the scene – big data is growing, an information treasure trove
- Explaining relevance of TDM - an opportunity to harness big data
- Posing the problem that the project aims to solve – not enough EU TDM
- Pushing the project – overcoming barriers to TDM and finding solutions "explore, analyse, improve"

The video will be promoted extensively on mailing lists, the project website, social media, the Open Information Hub and at project events. Partners will also be encouraged to promote the video

through their own communications channels. It will be designed to have impact beyond the end of the project lifespan and meet the sustainability objective of the exploitation plan.

Responsibility: LIBER will be responsible for producing the video with input from all partners.

Target: LIBER aims to produce the video by month 7. We aim to get 500 views by month 10 with new targets set at the first review stage.

12.3 FutureTDM Blog

From month 5, the blog will be visible on the home page of the project website, and will have its own web page accessible via the toolbar. It will be the most regularly updated point of information on the website. The blog will be written by the FutureTDM consortium as well as guest stakeholder contributors. WP7 will encourage the consortium to deliver these blogs on a regular basis.

In the first year of the project, the blog will aim to pique stakeholder interest in TDM, the project and its events and build a proactive TDM community that will be willing to get involved, feedback experiences in TDM and ultimately form part of the Open Information Hub platform. In the second year of the project the blogs will talk more about the FutureTDM project results, best practice and developments and opportunities associated with the Open Information Hub.

The blog style guide below is purposefully aligned with that of OpenMinTeD as it is hoped that these two projects will eventually share a blog space on the Open Information Hub website after month 14.

The blog articles can:

- Inform the TDM community about FutureTDM developments
- Inform the TDM community about FutureTDM events
- Engage the TDM community through opinion pieces that ask for feedback and create a discussion among the TDM community
- Increase awareness among stakeholders about the benefits of text-mining and the organisational, technical and legal limitations of machine access to research publications

Style of the blog

- Catchy title
- Captivating introduction paragraph
- At least 1 photo / picture / graph
- Highlight important sentences in bold (we can use these as quotes to stand out in the blog)
- Use sub headers to break up large blocks of text
- Add 5 -10 tags to represent the blog
- Maximum 2,000 words
- If possible, graphs, tables or infographics to explain complicated components
- If possible, link to related blogs posts, news posts, or scientific articles

- Mention words such as “TDM”, “Content Mining”, “copyright” and “Big Data” (for Search Engine Optimisation)

On the blog page of the website we may also feature blog posts from other projects and organisations, relevant to the aims of the FutureTDM project.

Responsibility: OK/CM will collect blogs from the consortium by setting specific deadlines for specific members. The consortium will be asked to write a blog after every attended event or workshop on TDM, and to update their colleagues once a month about their work in FutureTDM. WP7 will also encourage the consortium to take initiative to write blogs ad-hoc about text and data mining and to use the blog log on the shared drive. The leader of WP7, OK/CM, will set content deadlines for the consortium, will add blog-style headlines and edit the texts if necessary before publishing.

Targets: A blog should be posted at least once every two weeks. The success of the blog can be measured in the number of unique visits to the blog web page and comments generated. Targets will be set at first review stage.

12.4 Twitter

The most widely used form of social media in the TDM community is Twitter and the project will prioritise this social media channel in order to establish a strong social media presence.

A Twitter account is already set up and is accessible at <https://twitter.com/futuretdm>

Tweets about the project are to include @futuretdm and #futuretdm where relevant

Partners will be informed of the best times to post:

- Always on weekdays
- At the start of the workday
- During lunch breaks
- In the evening after 17.00 (commuting time)

Tweeting will regularly reflect our key messages by:

- Promoting Future TDM materials that map the TDM landscape (factsheets, papers, flyers)
- Promoting stakeholder engagement (upcoming events, blogs and surveys, stakeholder map)
- Promoting expertise, (the Open Information Hub, latest developments, events feedback, policy frameworks, roadmaps and best practice library)

Where possible, the tweets will be current (i.e. at or soon after the event), with visual content, to the point and catchy and encouraging engagement (not just one-way information sharing). Partners are encouraged to retweet the project’s tweets.

The project should follow (back) any organisation and/or individual relevant to TDM but try to avoid following unknown individuals or organisations that might result in spam tweets. All partners will have a responsibility to ensure that they do not bring the project into disrepute on twitter. The

@futuretdm account should always represent the project, never an organisation's or individual's own opinions.

Responsibility: SYNYO, LIBER and OK/CM will have direct access to the twitter account. Other partners should send their tweet suggestions to OK/CM who will have responsibility for ensuring that there are daily tweets. The partners are also encouraged to use their own twitter accounts to promote the project with #FutureTDM.

Targets: one tweet per working day, 400 followers by month 10 (at month 5 we had 100 followers). New targets will be set at first review stage.

12.5 Surveys

As outlined in deliverable 2.2 the project will conduct 30 face to face surveys, information will be absorbed and 10 will be selected as best practice case studies. However, the FutureTDM project wants to offer more opportunity for survey feedback than just 30 stakeholders. In addition to the face to face surveys, an online survey will be made available for any stakeholder to participate in. This will be initially placed and tested on the project website and then transferred to the Open Information Hub after month 14.

Stakeholders completing the survey will be able to see graphics resulting from the overall response results to quantitative questions. It is hoped that the project can also produce a video of short interview clips resulting from the knowledge cafés which will be shown at the Symposium and on the Open Information Hub. If this goes ahead, the knowledge café host will take responsibility for producing this video and interviewees will be given an authorization form asking for permission for their clip to be used.

Responsibility: Tasks may be delegated but OK/CM will be responsible for overseeing the development and look of the online survey and will supply the questions based on the face to face surveys and consultation with the other partners. The knowledge café hosts will be responsible for the mini videos.

Targets: 50 online survey responses by month 10. Targets to be revisited at review stage.

12.6 Dissemination Materials

As part of a Communications Dissemination Pack, the project aims to produce at least one TDM poster, project flyer and sticker for partners to take to external and project events. In addition, the project aims to produce two pop-up banners for project events to increase visibility and brand awareness. These items will reflect the key messages and/or brand of the project. Partners are also encouraged to promote the project at events and submitting conference papers and posters where possible. Further information on events dissemination materials can be found in the communication plan overview.

12.7 Newsletter

On the website is an option for interested stakeholders to sign up to the FutureTDM website. The aim of the Newsletter is to:

- Send traffic to websites, where more information on the project is available
- Create buzz about the project, by giving our target audience regular updates on all our activities
- Raise awareness of FutureTDM and TDM issues/activities
- Increase engagement; every newsletter will contain a call to action to get involved in FutureTDM

WP7 will collect all the relevant news, blogs and project updates of the last 3 months and select the most important and/or appealing elements to be highlighted in the newsletter. The newsletter will be kept short and will serve as a dissemination summary. Articles will contain an interesting headline and only the first paragraph or the overview of an article will appear in the newsletter. This enables our target audience to scan the content quickly, and then link out to read the full text. The letter will be made available in the resources section of the website and will be sent to the newsletter mailing list resulting from the sign up button on the home page of the website.

The newsletter will contain around six articles, each with a picture. For variety it may include:

- Interviews with the consortium about their work and the project progress
- Legislative or policy updates
- Text and data mining updates
- Calendar of events and poster presentations
- Selected blogs
- Link to Twitter

It will be promoted on the website and social media and will eventually be linked to the Open Information Hub website.

Responsibility: The leader of WP7, OK/CM, will be responsible for coordinating the creation of content and the collection and selection of the content and organising responsibility for setting up the sending out the newsletter i.e. via MailChimp. Partners are encouraged to make suggestions for improvement. OK/CM gives final approval and has overall editorial responsibility but may delegate some editorial tasks out to selected partners.

Targets: As of February 15th, the newsletter will be released quarterly. Content should be ready to be published by the 15th of month 6, 9, 12 and so on. The success of the newsletter can be measured in the number of sign ups. In month 10 we hope to have 100 sign ups with new targets set at first review stage.

12.8 Mailing Lists

The Newsletter mailing list will be used for updates about the project. However, a mailing list based on the stakeholder directory will be created for the purpose of sending invitations to the knowledge cafés, workshops and Symposium. General dissemination of project developments will be done via twitter.

13 PROMOTING BEST PRACTICE AND EXPERTISE

In year two of the project, emphasis shifts away from barriers to TDM and towards best practice and opportunities. In this phase it is hoped that the consortium can draw from expertise to produce fact sheets and publications that promote case studies and explore solutions that might improve TDM uptake in the EU. Partners will log their planned publications in the shared drive. The FutureTDM project itself is a solution in that it brings together expertise and the TDM stakeholder community. At the Symposium event we would like to show stakeholders how we have progressed as a project by producing an infographic representation of the feedback from our investigations. This can then be used to promote the project beyond its September 2017 end date. The symposium will also represent an opportunity to showcase the training sessions developed by OK/CM. Here stakeholders will have a chance to experience TDM in practice and improve their TDM understanding.

Further information relating to methods promoting best practice can be found in the communication plan overview.

14 PRESS RELATIONS

A press list will be created as part of the stakeholder directory.

If contacted by the press in relation to the project, partners will inform the work package lead OK/CM. In communicating with the press as a representative of FutureTDM, partners will ensure that they represent the project and not an individual's or an organisation's own opinion.

Press releases will be sent to our press list at major moments in the FutureTDM project. These may include:

- Workshops
- Symposium
- Open Information Hub launch

Responsibility: Press releases will always go through LIBER for editing, be approved by the WP7 lead OK/CM who will also format the press release and send out to the press list.

Targets: At least 3 press releases in the project lifespan. Success can be measured by the number of articles published on the basis of each press release.

15 OVERALL COMMUNICATIONS AND DISSEMINATION RESPONSIBILITIES

OK/CM as work package lead has overall responsibility for the dissemination activities and will:

- Coordinate the preparation and final editing of the quarterly newsletter
- Provide information on dissemination progress
- Coordinate the drafting of dissemination materials

The dissemination activities will be executed in close cooperation with all the project partners who are involved in WP7. Where relevant and for maximum efficiency, OK/CM may delegate tasks to the other partners listed in WP7.

Every work package leader should come each month with a blog post.

The work package leaders should make sure that the content of the news item / blog post focuses on the overall results of their work package.

They should also assist WP7 effectiveness by alerting OK/CM to information on:

- Events where project results can be promoted
- Publications in journals, conferences
- Related articles
- Related projects
- Related work of individual researchers
- Deliverables completed

16 EXPLOITATION PLAN

The Communications Plan for the FutureTDM project does not end in September 2017. One of the goals of the plan is to ensure the relevance of the project after its end date, in particular, the long-term sustainability and usability of the platform, policy framework, and practitioner guidelines. To achieve sustainability the project will require a successful Open Information Hub platform and a message that is meaningful throughout and beyond its lifespan. Crucially, it needs to build a strong TDM community, including with other projects, so that stakeholders have a vested interest in ensuring that FutureTDM's goals be carried forward.

16.1 An Invested TDM Community

TDM is a new and innovative technology with a big future. It is anticipated that given the important and topical nature of content mining, there will be further TDM relevant projects that can benefit from the expertise gleaned and community built. It is therefore our aim to ensure that we leave a thriving, informative, collaborating platform that can adapt to work with future projects post September 2017.

One of the key features of FutureTDM is its focus on engaging with stakeholders and building good relations with other projects and in particular OpenMinTeD. By involving and building the stakeholder community from the early stages of the project, it is expected that there will be a solid platform of TDM individuals and organisations that share the goals of the project and proactively want it to continue.

16.2 Sustainability in Practice

It is anticipated that the stakeholder engagement emphasis will ensure the establishment of a strong TDM community that will be able to continue to provide the Open Information Hub with up to date content and ensure social media promotion. In the second year of the project, the consortium will be looking to strengthen ties with other longer running projects that can help to communicate the project achievements and opportunities beyond September 2017.

The legacy of the project is The Open Information Hub. It will live longer than the project run of two years. WP6 will use a commonly used CMS for the content of this website to ensure that it is user friendly. SYNIO will be a crucial component in ensuring the sustainability of the Open Information Hub and will be responsible for hosting and running the portal after the project ends. To make sure that the Open Information Hub has relevance not just to FutureTDM but to all open TDM projects in the future, the Open Information Hub may be assigned more than one domain name.

The FutureTDM project will be operating side by side (often jointly) with the OpenMinTeD project which runs until May 2018. The two projects have partners in common (LIBER, UvA, ARC) and so it makes sense in months after the FutureTDM project end date, to have one of these project partners or OpenMinTeD itself take a vested interest in the Open Information Hub site with a view to having the Open Information Hub included in an upcoming TDM related project.

A **sustainability round table** will be organised virtually between the projects early in the Open Information Hub development stages to ensure it has project compatibility. This has been scheduled for the 9th of February 2016. A physical round table will take place by one month ahead of the symposium between OpenMinTed, FutureTDM and any other projects or organisations who have expressed an interest in the running of the Open Information Hub post September 2017. This meeting will decide the responsibilities of the Open Information Hub so that this information can be relayed at the FutureTDM Symposium. A third meeting may be scheduled in the months between the Symposium and end date of the project to finalise the arrangement.

Finally, some of the project communications tools will be designed so that they are not just limited to the project deliverables, defined by a timeframe or end goal. Instead the collaboration aspect of the project and the website will be emphasised. In particular, promotional items linked to the TDM community and the Open Information Hub will be designed with this in mind (e.g. the video and infographic).

17 MONITORING AND MEASURING SUCCESS

The success of our stakeholder engagement and media publicity efforts will be seen through continuous improvements in a number of measurable areas including:

- Blog posts and comments
- Responses to our surveys
- Attendees at our workshops, knowledge cafés and presentations
- Feedback post events via satisfaction surveys
- Project newsletter subscribers
- Number of mentions in other media channels
- Twitter followers
- Web site visits

These will be recorded based on the Communications Plan table (annex 1).

A Review in Month 10

The plan has been designed to be reviewed after month 10 so that we can improve communications, step up efforts if targets are not met or set more ambitious targets for year two if the project is going well. The review, overseen by OK/CM, will include an update of the communications plan table where targets can be set against actual achievements. A **Summary Report** deliverable (7.4) in month 24 will assess the effectiveness of the communications strategy based on this review, the targets set and their measurements.

18 CONCLUSION

The FutureTDM Communication and Exploitation Plan has inclusion at its core. With a strategy that is not just about one way dissemination but designed to engage and build an invested and proactive TDM community – the Open Information Hub, the plan is also about ensuring project sustainability post September 2017.

By combining strong messaging, accessible communications methods and expert analysis, we are confident that we can reach the broadest possible range of organisations, individual stakeholders and end users with an interest in the work and outcomes of FutureTDM. This in turn will maximise our prospects in addressing the project goal – to reduce barriers to TDM uptake in the EU.

ANNEX 1: COMMUNICATION PLAN OVERVIEW

Because of the variety of activities, forums and project phases, a user friendly summary of communications activities is available below in the Communications Plan Overview. This will be extended at Review stage so that new targets can be added.

What do we plan to produce?	Explanation	Further notes	Responsibility	Where	When expected	Target
Over the whole project lifespan:						
Social media	Strong and relevant social media presence to publicise the project in real time	Twitter – the most widely used form of social media in the TDM community	SYNYO, LIBER, OK/CM to have direct access, OK/CM responsible for ensuring daily tweets. Partners re-tweet or suggest tweets to OK/CM	Twitter	Set up in month 2, daily tweets from month 5	500 tweets, 400 followers by month 10
Blog	Where stakeholders can find latest updates on the project and useful info	Home page of project website as well as Blog page within project website and then home page of Open Information Hub from month 15	SYNYO to create and moderate. All to write blogs on events attended, tasks completed, raising awareness and encouraging feedback. OK/CM to oversee, final approval	Project website and Open Information Hub	From month 5	At least one blog every two weeks, one external blog per month. Success measured by visits and comments
Project Website	Main point of project visibility until the Open Information Hub goes online	Info about the project, partners, events, resources, dissemination, survey	SYNYO	Project website	Month 2	500 unique visits, 1000 total per month

		and the blog				
Templates	Logo, Power point and press release templates for partners to use	Ensuring brand continuity	SYNYO	Shared document space	Month 2	NA
Newsletter	Improve traffic to websites, where more information on the project is available. regular updates on all our activities	Aim is to raise awareness and increase engagement . Every newsletter will contain a call to action to get involved in FutureTDM, Open Information Hub and events	OKCM will be responsible for coordinating the content, mail out and has overall editorial responsibility	Mailing lists, project website OK/CM to delegate, Open Information Hub	Released quarterly. Content should be ready to be published by the 15th of month 6, 9, 12, and so on	Success measured in the number of sign ups. 100 sign ups by month 10 with new targets set at first review stage.
Fact Sheets	To support the work of the project and encourage feedback i.e. at events.	Can be suggested and drafted by partners in accordance with their WP or the overall project. For example, what is TDM? What are best practice case studies?	All	Project website and Open Information Hub, project events	As of month 6 and throughout the project	NA

Project Reports	Reports resulting from the work packages	Highlighting findings e.g. relating to legal, economic landscape	Relating to WPs	Project website and Open Information Hub, project events	As in DOA	N/A
PHASE 1 (YEAR 1) explaining the project to stakeholders, and getting their input						
Project infographic video	Video of project description based on DoW	Useful for events showcasing project	SYNYO	Project website, Open Information Hub, social media	Month 2	NA
A4 FTDM cards	Promo card of project description based on DoW	Useful for events showcasing project	SYNYO	Project/external events, project website	Month 2	NA
Knowledge café flyer	Explaining knowledge cafés and asking for input	Making events more accessible	OK/CM to draft, SYNYO to put online	For website and email lists	Month 6	NA
FTDM conference poster	Poster for conferences	Explanation of project aims and objectives	Any partner in collaboration with SYNYO (branding)	Project and external events	When applicable - event related	3 posters at conferences
Option-more plain language user friendly leaflet	Explaining project in clear accessible language. Call to action	Possibly drawing from video	If mirroring video - LIBER	Project and external events	Month 7	NA

Survey on website	Reflecting the 30 surveys face to face	Opportunity for opinion feedback online	SYNYO will be responsible for development and look of the survey, OK/CM will supply the questions based on the face to face surveys and consultation with the other partners	Project website and Open Information Hub	By month 8	50 responses by month 10
Video	Approx. 2 minute video, fun, reaching out to stakeholders explaining TDM and why FTDM is of interest to them	Crucial to the project if we are to be inclusive and what to promote project widely	LIBER	Mailing lists, project website, social media, Open Information Hub, project events	Month 7	500 views by month 10
Roll up banner stands	Two banners with FTDM logo and slogan for use at knowledge cafés, workshops and symposium and where needed at events	Reinforcing the brand and our visibility at events Making us look more professional, easy to locate. Good as background for photos and videos	WP7 lead to coordinate the task between SYNYO (logo etc.), OK/CM (task management) and one other partner (content)	Project events	By month 7	2 banner stands

FTDM general poster	For events	To raise brand visibility i.e. at event stands	WP7 lead to coordinate the task between SYNYO (logo etc.), OK/CM (task management) and one other partner (content)	Project and external events	By month 7	NA
FTDM Sticker	Fun promotional item	FutureTDM sticker (i.e. for laptops)	WP7 lead to coordinate the task between SYNYO (logo etc.), OK/CM (task management) and one other partner (content)	Project and external events	By month 7	NA
Dissemination pack	Pack of dissemination items for each partner	Poster, flyers and stickers	OK/CM to coordinate	Project and external events	Sent by month 7	To be coordinated between partners and OK/CM
PHASE 2 (YEAR 2): promoting best practice and the Open Information Hub						
Open Information Hub	The go-to website for EU TDM stakeholders. A WP6 deliverable but too relevant not to be mentioned	Provide practical, legal and policy information on TDM, information on barriers and solutions to	SYNYO	futuretdm.eu may also be assigned other domain names	Month 14 first roll out	Targets to be set at first review

	here. Providing TDM information and collaboration space.	TDM Promoting TDM through best practices Encouraging online debate about TDM				
Publications	Project related articles in TDM publications	To promote our findings and reflecting TDM expertise	Any partner can contribute	Open access publications	At any point of the project	At least 2
Conference papers	Where relevant	Highlighting the project at conference events in response to call for papers	Any partner can contribute	At relevant conferences and their websites	At any point of the project	NA
Press releases	Press releases will be sent to our press list at major moments in the FutureTDM project	These may include: Workshops Symposium Open Information Hub launch	Press releases will always go through LIBER for editing, be approved by OK/CM and sent out to the press list. SYNYO will assist in the format of the press release	Social media, mailing lists, with news releases on project website, Open Information Hub	When relevant	Targets to be set at first review
Info graphic	For promoting	A key communicat	LIBER	Project website,	Before Symposium	Targets to be set at

	our achievements at the end of the project - what we have learned	ions item to aim towards, promoting our achievements and for use post project		Open Information Hub, project events	m	first review
Mini video - collection of snippets from events?	Making the project more approachable and relevant to the stakeholder community	Asking KC attendees for short feedback sound bites, putting them on the website	OK/CM and LIBER to draw up a plan and delegate responsibility	To be unveiled at symposium, Open Information Hub, project website, social media, mailing lists	Collected between month 6-11, ready by month 14	N/A

NA = not applicable i.e. where amounts are dependent on external or variable factors